

Trends in Agriculture Productivity In India

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Introduction:

Indian agriculture sector was very much backward and stagnant since at the time of independence. Even since the launching of the first five years plan During the year 1951 to 1956 Indian Agricultural sector has received the prime attrition of the central government as well as the state government in the overall strategy of social economic development of the economy. As result of all this factors Indian agriculture productivity has been increase over the years and the economy

has achieved high degree of self efficiency in terms of food grains and raw materials for agro based industry also.

Objective of the Study

1. To study agriculture productivity in India

Research Methodology:

This paper based on secondary data which is collected from different secondary resources.

Table 1.1: Trends in the Productivity of Indian agriculture sector(yield per hectare)

Crop	1960-61	1970-71	1980-81	1990-91	2003-2004
Rice (kg)	1013	1123	1336	1740	2051
Wheat (kg)	851	1307	1630	2281	2707
Sugercane (tannes)	46	48	58	65	67
Cotton (kg)	125	106	152	225	307

Sources: Government of India economic survey 2004-05

This table shows that the trends in the productivity of Indian agriculture(yield hector) The statistics shoes that per hector aid a price is increased from 1031kg in 1960-61 to 2051kg in 2003-2004 and the production of wheat from 851 kg to 2707 kg over the same period was increased.

The yield per hector of sugarcane major plantation crop is also increase from 46 tonnes 1960-61 to 59 tonnes in 2003-2004. All together per hectare and major crops has increased over the last

four decades at it is for below the international levels. this scenario consider for an examination of the causes of low productivity of agriculture in India.

Table number 1.2 focused on the comparative yield of principal crops in various countries. The reason of to provide disable is only the purpose of to understand the comparative analysis of different yield of principal crops in various countries so that we understand the status of productivity of Indian agriculture sector.

Table 1.2 : Comparative yield of principal crops in various countries for the year 1999 (kg per hector)

Country	paddy	Wheat	maize	Groundnut	Sugare cane
India	2929	2583	1667	913	68012
China	6321	3969	4880	2799	85294
Japan	6414	-----	-----	2336	-----
USA	6622	2872	8398	3038	80787
Indonesia	4261	-----	2646	1523	-----
Canada	—	2591	7974	-----	-----
Vietnam	4105	-----	-----	1435	-----
world average	3845	2711	4313	1336	65680

Source: Government of India Planning Commission 10th Five year plan (2002 to 2007) Volume II p.515

Table Number 1.2 It clearly shows that the status of Indian agriculture productivity is very low as compare with China, Japan, USA, Indonesia, Canada and Vietnam. this comparative analysis is regarding different countries and various principle crops for the year 1999 this is measured in KG per Hector.

The given statistical data shows that there is huge gap In Indian agriculture productivity. because of several reasons Indian agriculture productivity is very low as comparative with above said countries. At world level with comparative analysis of yield of principal crops we can say that the

productivity of Indian agriculture sector was very low. not only that After the 75 years of independence the share of agriculture in GDP it has also Fallen significantly and as a result the average GDP has become reactly less Sensitive to fluctuations in agriculture performance. this factor is of course well recognised but the role of agriculture and specially Agriculture Income influencing GDPgrowth directly or Indirectly through the demand side is less well understood.

Table Number 1.3 it shows that the share of agriculture in GDP and the share of non food consumption in rural exponditures over the last three decades.

Table No 1.3: Decline mean share of agriculture in GDP (percent)

Year	Share of Agriculture In GDP	Share of non-food in rural Expenditures
1973-74	44.0	25.1
1983	38.7	34.4
1993-94	32.9	36.8
1999-2000	26.9	40.6

Source: Government of India, Planning Commission 10th five year plan(2002-2007) Vol-I P.28

Table Number 1.3 it show that the how agriculture sector have decline share in GDP of the economy in the last 3-4 decades. as can be seen how the agriculture share in GDP has Decline from

44% in 1973-74 to 27 % 1999-2000 but at the same time non food expenditure of the people has Increase food 25 % in1973-74 to near by 41 % in 1999-2000. In Other words 5% change in the growth

of agriculture would have affected GDP growth rate by 0.44% in 1973-74 but only by 0.27% in 1999-2000. At the same time the indirect efforts of Change in agriculture growth Therefore the demand for non agricultural goods and services has actually increased. in the future as average Agriculture Income increase this indirect efforts of Agriculture Income on non agricultural growth will be come more strong. Directly now we can say that day by day rural area and their income will be more spent on non agricultural goods and services and not on food. It will be More negative part for overall agriculture development in country.

Now we discuss the main causes of low productivity of Indian agriculture sector. there are so many factors responsible for low productivity of agriculture but we consider major aspects it will be divided in two Main parts which explain of in following ways and means there is so need to explanation and your factor in much details will take point to point and understand why and how their causes are responsible for low agriculture productivity

I Technical factors

- lack of irrigation facilities
- Limited use of fertilizers
- Limited use of HYV seeds
- inadequate plant protection schemes
- flours and soil erosion

II Institutional factors

- Human factors
- Small size Holdings
- Financial issues
- Marketing difficulties ect.....

Low productivity in Indian agriculture is the result of a number of

Technology traditional factors which influence each other.

Suggestions to measures increase productivity of Indian Agriculture

1. The farmers should be provided with a stable price for their agricultural products at a remunerative level.
2. There should be an expansion of adequate marketing facilities to sell the agricultural product.
3. The land tenure system should be changed in favour of the cultivator.
4. There should be a provision of cheap credit on reasonable terms especially to small farmers for better techniques of production.
5. The modern inputs like fertilizers. Pesticides and improved seeds should be made available to the farmers at reasonable prices.
6. There should be provisions of education, research and extension of agro-economic services to spread the knowledge of improved methods of farming.
7. The State should make provision for the development of resources which are not possible in the part of individual farmers e.g. large scale irrigation, land reclamation or resettlement projects.
8. There should be an extension of land used and intensification and utilization of land already in use through improved and scientific implements.

Conclusion:

If we want our Indian agriculture to grow and boom in the coming years, then we have to take crucial steps for their advancement. The steps must

include knowledge, resources, and required market access to the Indian farmers. Agriculture & farming is not just about food security; it's more about building a prosperous future for the generations to come

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